

Supporting Information for

"Molecular dynamics simulations of asphaltene aggregation: machine learning identification of representative molecules, molecular polydispersity and inhibitor performance"

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1 Digitalization of the catalogue of model molecules

In order to accelerate the digitalization of the molecules proposed by Law et al.¹ via 2D representations, we have used an open-source optical chemical structure recognition (OCSR) Java-based tool called MolVec.² As in general the accuracy of OCSR tools rarely exceeds 90%,³ we have taken extra precautions to ensure that the original 2D structures were properly captured, and when necessary manual modifications were applied to match it. One way of verifying that the digitalized structures are consistent with the original 2D representations is to compare their chemical formulas. On this point, we have noticed some inconsistencies in the original material released as Supporting Information:¹

- Discrepancies are present between the chemical formulas of the summary Table A1 of Law et al.¹ and the chemical formulas reported below each model molecule. Their Table A1 contains 25 errors of this sort, for which the correct chemical formulas are reported below the concerned molecules and hereafter between parenthesis: A24 ($C_{72}H_{71}NS_2$), A26 ($C_{71}H_{59}NS_2$), A27 ($C_{72}H_{67}NS_2$), A29 ($C_{69}H_{53}NS_2$), A30 ($C_{73}H_{63}NS_2$), A52 ($C_{64}H_{69}N$), A55 ($C_{44}H_{47}N$), A58 ($C_{55}H_{50}$), A69 ($C_{45}H_{32}N_4$), A71 ($C_{78}H_{93}NS_2$), A72 ($C_{64}H_{75}NS_2$), A73 ($C_{68}H_{77}NOS$), A74 ($C_{57}H_{69}NOS$), A75 ($C_{65}H_{71}NS_2$), A76 ($C_{59}H_{69}NOS_2$), A77 ($C_{61}H_{69}NOS$), A78 ($C_{79}H_{83}NOS$), A79 ($C_{68}H_{77}NOS$), A80 ($C_{86}H_{95}NS_4$), A83 ($C_{62}H_{65}NOS_2$), A84 ($C_{52}H_{59}NOS_2$), A85 ($C_{55}H_{65}NOS_3$), A86 ($C_{81}H_{71}NS$), A87 ($C_{52}H_{59}NOS$), and A89 ($C_{64}H_{69}NOS_2$).
- 9 molecules have erroneous chemical formulas (wrong number of H atoms) both in the summary Table A1 and below each model molecule. Corrected formulas are provided here: A3 ($C_{68}H_{75}NS_2$), A9 ($C_{67}H_{81}NS_2$), A11 ($C_{68}H_{67}NS_2$), A12 ($C_{68}H_{85}NS_2$), A13 ($C_{56}H_{37}N$), A38 ($C_{73}H_{77}NS_1$), A41 ($C_{51}H_{43}N$), A46 ($C_{62}H_{69}N$), and A88 ($C_{67}H_{71}NOS$). In these cases great attention has been dedicated to ensuring the digitalized structures match the 2D representations.
- For molecule A82, the chemical formula accounts for 4 S atoms whereas it only contains

3 (fourth S has probably been swapped with a C atom) and for an incorrect number of H atoms. The final corrected chemical formula is $C_{67}H_{75}NS_3$.

2 Unsupervised machine learning analysis

Once the catalogue of 100 model molecules¹ has been digitalized and 3D molecular descriptors have been calculated, our objective was to identify groups of similar asphaltene molecules in order to select a few representative models. To do so, unsupervised machine learning (ML) approaches, namely dimensionality reduction and cluster analysis, have been used. In this process, the clustering can either be performed on data of high dimensionality or on reduced dimensionality data. For the catalogue of 100 model molecules, the principal component analysis⁴ (PCA) decomposition shows that the first 60 components capture more than 99% of the explained variance ratio. Therefore, in what follows we have compared clustering analysis performed either on 60 PCA components or on 3 PCA components, the latter accounting for a total of a 68.2% of the explained variance ratio. Moreover, the assignation of clusters according to the following three clustering algorithms implemented in the scikit-learn library⁵ have been compared: Kmeans, Gaussian mixture (GM) and Ward. With these algorithms, the number of clusters the unsupervised ML model will assign is an input parameter of the model. In this work, we have compared models assigning 2 to 10 clusters. To evaluate the performances of the different clustering strategies we relied on three metrics:

- The silhouette coefficient (SC), which adopts values in the range [-1;1]. Silhouette analysis studies the separation distance between resulting clusters. The higher the score, the better defined are the clusters.
- The Calinski-Harabasz (CH) index (variance ratio criterion) is the ratio of the sum of intra-clusters dispersion and of inter-cluster dispersion for all clusters, where dispersion is defined as the sum of distances squared. The higher the score, the better defined are the clusters.
- The Davies-Bouldin (DB) index captures the average "similarity" between clusters, where the similarity is a measure that compares the distance between clusters with the

size of the clusters themselves. The closer to 0, the better is the partition in clusters.

Table S1 and Table S2 present the values of these metrics for the cluster analyses performed with the three algorithms previously mentioned, done on 3 and 60 PCA components, respectively. The tables show that, in both cases, the three algorithms perform very similarly and that cluster assignments of a number of clusters between 4 and 8 are in the same range of performance.

Table S1: Three clustering metrics: silhouette coefficient (SC), Calinski-Harabasz (CH) index, and Davies-Bouldin (DB) index; for Kmeans, Gaussian mixture (GM) and Ward cluster analysis performed on 3 PCA components.

# of clusters	Kmeans			GM			Ward		
	SC	CH	DB	SC	CH	DB	SC	CH	DB
2	0.396	58.0	1.170	0.333	43.1	1.397	0.500	56.3	0.607
3	0.401	73.1	0.955	0.426	67.2	0.768	0.426	67.2	0.768
4	0.486	107.1	0.708	0.394	76.0	0.955	0.482	105.4	0.724
5	0.527	126.5	0.590	0.526	125.7	0.592	0.525	124.7	0.596
6	0.493	129.8	0.666	0.480	125.1	0.673	0.496	125.7	0.711
7	0.487	128.0	0.702	0.461	116.0	0.712	0.488	123.6	0.739
8	0.472	124.9	0.738	0.431	62.9	1.056	0.468	118.5	0.773
9	0.423	119.8	0.809	0.365	99.3	1.160	0.387	117.4	0.875
10	0.427	121.5	0.854	0.369	100.0	1.142	0.385	116.2	0.893

Table S2: Three clustering metrics: silhouette coefficient (SC), Calinski-Harabasz (CH) index, and Davies-Bouldin (DB) index; for Kmeans, Gaussian mixture (GM) and Ward cluster analysis performed on 60 PCA components.

# of clusters	Kmeans			GM			Ward		
	SC	CH	DB	SC	CH	DB	SC	CH	DB
2	0.277	33.8	1.584	0.263	30.1	1.656	0.380	33.5	0.946
3	0.244	34.9	1.440	0.244	34.9	1.444	0.269	33.4	1.250
4	0.282	37.9	1.263	0.245	35.2	1.351	0.278	36.3	1.228
5	0.282	37.3	1.174	0.283	37.3	1.167	0.276	35.8	1.222
6	0.263	33.8	1.324	0.253	33.8	1.352	0.249	33.5	1.354
7	0.244	30.5	1.500	0.214	29.4	1.463	0.244	30.5	1.356
8	0.234	28.3	1.405	0.208	28.2	1.549	0.241	28.4	1.380
9	0.205	26.2	1.623	0.204	25.9	1.605	0.223	26.2	1.400
10	0.192	23.9	1.633	0.171	23.7	1.680	0.220	24.5	1.394

To further investigate the effect of performing the cluster analysis on 3 or 60 PCA components, Figure S1 displays 3D PCA representations of the catalogue of 100 molecules with

colouring according to cluster assignments from Kmeans cluster analysis assigning 4 clusters, performed on 3 PCA components (panel a) and on 60 PCA components (panel b). Cluster 1 and 3 are swapped between the 3 and 60 components analysis, therefore the colouring has been adapted accordingly, to show that the assignment is actually identical in both cases.

Figure S1: 3D PCA representations of the catalogue of 100 molecules with colouring according to cluster assignments from Kmeans cluster analysis assigning 4 clusters, performed on 3 PCA components (panel a) and on 60 PCA components (panel b).

When the Kmeans algorithm is set up to assign 5 clusters, there are only two molecules, A24 and A27, which are assigned differently from the analysis performed on 3 (panel a)) and 60 (panel b)) components. As shown in Figure S2, molecules A24 and A27, circled by a dash line, are at the frontier between clusters. Here again, colouring has been adapted to compensate for clusters swapping between the two analysis.

In Figure S3, Kmeans analysis performed on 3 components (panel a)) and Gaussian mixture performed on 60 components (panel b)) are compared when set up to assign 5 clusters. In that case the only difference in assignment is molecule A35, within a dash line circle, which is again at the frontier between clusters. Figure S2 and Figure S3 show that there are only a few differences in the assignment, namely at the frontier between clusters, depending on how the cluster analysis is performed.

Furthermore, to ensure that the clustering analysis was not biased by the PCA dimensionality reduction, the assignments of Kmeans cluster analysis, set up to assign 5 (panel a)) and 7 (panel b)) clusters from the 3 PCA components, are represented in Figure S4 on

Figure S2: 3D PCA representations of the catalogue of 100 molecules with colouring according to cluster assignments from Kmeans cluster analysis assigning 5 clusters, performed on 3 PCA components (panel a) and on 60 PCA components (panel b).

Figure S3: 3D PCA representations of the catalogue of 100 molecules with colouring according to cluster assignments from Kmeans cluster analysis assigning 5 clusters performed on 3 PCA components (panel a) and from Gaussian mixture clustering performed on 60 PCA components (panel b).

different representations, namely 3D representations of a uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP) dimensionality reduction.⁶ Conversely to PCA, UMAP is a non-linear dimensionality reduction method, which has shown great performance in capturing the underlying structure of the data. Interestingly, the cluster assignments performed on 3 PCA components match very well the data structure shown by UMAP. In both 5 and 7 clusters assignments, only two molecules, circled by a dashed line, seem incorrectly assigned. These two molecules are A24 and A27, therefore panel a) of Figure S4 agrees with panel b) of Figure S2 in which the cluster analysis has been performed on 60 PCA dimensions.

Figure S4: 3D UMAP representations of the catalogue of 100 molecules with colouring according to cluster assignments from Kmeans cluster analysis, assigning, respectively, 5 clusters (panel a) and 7 (panel b) clusters from cluster analysis performed on 3 PCA components.

All in all, this in-depth study of the cluster assignments demonstrates that, in this case, the cluster algorithm and the dimensionality of the data only affect a few molecules at the frontier between clusters and that assignments of a number of clusters between 4 and 8 are in the same range of performance. Therefore, the selection of molecules for the molecular dynamics (MD) study has been based on a Kmeans cluster analysis performed on 3 PCA component to assign 7 clusters. Additionally, we have ensured that none of the selected molecules were at the frontier between clusters, to avoid being affected by the setup of the

clustering analysis. Here below, the composition of the clusters are provided, along with general descriptions of the molecules they comprise and with the molecules selected for the MD study highlighted bold and displayed in Figure 1:

- Cluster #0 assembles archipelago asphaltenes with many heterocycles: A70, A72, A73, A74, A75, A76, A77, A79, A81, A82, A83, A84, **A85**, A87, A88, and A89.
- Cluster #1 assembles island asphaltenes: A7, A35, A43, A46, A48, A49, A52, A55, A56, A57, A58, A60, A62, **A63**, A64, A66, and A68.
- Cluster #2 assembles island asphaltenes with short sidechains and many heterocycles: A13, A41, A42, A44, A45, A47, A50, A51, A53, **A54**, A59, A61, A65, A67, and A69.
- Cluster #3 assembles the resins: A90, A91, A92, A93, A94, A95, A96, A97, A98, A99, and A100.
- Cluster #4 assembles very large archipelago asphaltenes: A71, A78, **A80**, and A86.
- Cluster #5 assembles island asphaltenes with long sidechains and 1 heterocycle: A1, A2, **A3**, A4, A5, A6, A8, A9, A10, A11, A12, A14, A15, A16, A17, A18, A19, A20, A21, A24, A27, A36, A37, A38, A39, and A40.
- Cluster #6 assembles the most bulky island asphaltenes. They have a medium length sidechains and 1 heterocycle: A22, A23, A25, A26, A28, **A29**, A30, A31, A32, A33, and A34.

3 Single asphaltene model systems

In this section we report the results of all single asphaltene model molecular dynamics simulations of asphaltene aggregation performed in this study. Table S3 and Table S4 summarize all observables from single asphaltene model simulations with 40 and 200 asphaltene molecules, while simulations with 100 asphaltene are reported in the main text (Table 1). Figure S5 to Figure S9 display the aggregation numbers from the simulations and Figures S10 to Figure S18 show the radius of gyration, estimated density, and relative shape anisotropy of the clusters over the last 40 ns. Figure S19 and Figure S20 reports the extension up to 500 ns of simulations of 200 molecules of A3 and of 200 molecules of A29 in heptane, respectively.

Table S3: Summary of the single asphaltene model simulations performed with 40 asphaltene molecules. For the aggregation number, g_n^{240} , we report the 20 ns average window at the end of the simulation. For the radius of gyration, R_g (in Å), the estimated density and the relative shape anisotropy, κ^2 , we report the average value over the last 40 ns of the simulations.

asph.	solvent	g_n^{240}	av. R_g	av. density	av. κ^2
A3	toluene	7.6 ± 0.5	14.3 ± 1.6	0.4 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
A3	heptane	40.0 ± 0.0	28.3 ± 0.9	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1
A29	toluene	29.2 ± 3.7	22.4 ± 6.5	0.4 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1
A29	heptane	40.0 ± 0.0	31.4 ± 1.6	0.4 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0
A54	toluene	4.1 ± 0.1	9.5 ± 0.8	0.5 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
A54	heptane	19.8 ± 1.3	17.0 ± 3.4	0.4 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.1
A63	toluene	3.7 ± 0.1	11.8 ± 1.3	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1
A63	heptane	4.8 ± 0.2	11.4 ± 1.5	0.4 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
A80	toluene	3.1 ± 0.1	15.2 ± 1.5	0.2 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1
A80	heptane	8.7 ± 0.8	18.7 ± 3.1	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.1
A85	toluene	3.7 ± 0.2	13.1 ± 1.4	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.1
A85	heptane	23.2 ± 4.1	18.8 ± 6.1	0.3 ± 0.1	0.2 ± 0.1

Table S4: Summary of the single asphaltene model simulations performed with 200 asphaltene molecules. For the aggregation number, g_n^{240} , we report the 20 ns average window at the end of the simulation. For the radius of gyration, R_g (in Å), the estimated density and the relative shape anisotropy, κ^2 , we report the average value over the last 40 ns of the simulations.

asph.	solvent	g_n^{240}	av. R_g	av. density	av. κ^2
A3	toluene	6.7 ± 0.3	13.6 ± 0.7	0.4 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
A3	heptane	28.2 ± 1.5	21.9 ± 1.3	0.4 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0
A29	toluene	40.8 ± 0.7	27.1 ± 2.7	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
A29	heptane	66.8 ± 0.3	26.8 ± 0.8	0.4 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
A63	toluene	3.5 ± 0.0	11.3 ± 0.5	0.3 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0
A63	heptane	6.4 ± 0.1	12.4 ± 0.6	0.4 ± 0.0	0.2 ± 0.0

Figure S5: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from single asphaltene model simulations of 40 molecules of asphaltene in toluene. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S6: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from single asphaltene model simulations of 40 molecules of asphaltene in heptane. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S7: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from single asphaltene model simulations of 100 molecules of asphaltene in toluene. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S8: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from single asphaltene model simulations of 100 molecules of asphaltene in heptane. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S9: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from single asphaltene model simulations of 200 molecules of asphaltene in toluene and in heptane. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S10: Radius of gyration of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 40 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S11: Radius of gyration of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 100 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S12: Radius of gyration of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 200 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S13: Estimated density of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 40 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S14: Estimated density of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 100 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S15: Estimated density of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 200 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S16: Relative shape anisotropy of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 40 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S17: Relative shape anisotropy of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 100 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S18: Relative shape anisotropy of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of single asphaltene model simulations of 200 molecules in heptane and toluene.

Figure S19: Aggregation number, g_n , (top left) from 500 ns simulations of 200 molecules of A3 in heptane. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics. The distributions of the properties of the asphaltene clusters are also represented, namely the radius of gyration (top right), the estimated density (bottom left) and the relative shape anisotropy (bottom right), accumulated over the last 40 ns of the simulations.

Figure S20: Aggregation number, g_n , (top left) from 500 ns simulations of 200 molecules of A29 in heptane. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics. The distributions of the properties of the asphaltene clusters are also represented, namely the radius of gyration (top right), the estimated density (bottom left) and the relative shape anisotropy (bottom right), accumulated over the last 40 ns of the simulations.

Figure S21: Snapshot from single asphaltene model simulations of 100 molecules of A3 in heptane after 220 ns. Carbon atoms are represented in gray, Nitrogen atoms in blue, Sulfur atoms in yellow and hydrogen atoms in white.

Figure S22: Snapshot from single asphaltene model simulations of 100 molecules of A29 in heptane after 220 ns. Carbon atoms are represented in gray, Nitrogen atoms in blue, Sulfur atoms in yellow and hydrogen atoms in white.

Figure S23: Snapshot from single asphaltene model simulations of 100 molecules of A85 in heptane after 220 ns. Carbon atoms are represented in gray, Nitrogen atoms in blue, Sulfur atoms in yellow and hydrogen atoms in white.

4 Mixtures of asphaltene: effect of molecular polydispersity

In this section we report the results of all molecular dynamics simulations of the aggregation of asphaltene mixtures performed in this work. Figure S24 to Figure S28 report the ternary mixture and Figure S29 to Figure S33 concern the quaternary mixtures. The compositions of the systems can be summarized as follow:

- $T1 = 34 \times A63 + 33 \times A80 + 33 \times A85$
- $T2 = 34 \times A3 + 33 \times A29 + 33 \times A85$
- $T3 = 34 \times A3 + 33 \times A54 + 33 \times A85$
- $T4 = 34 \times A3 + 33 \times A29 + 33 \times A54$
- $Q1 = 25 \times A3 + 25 \times A29 + 25 \times A54 + 25 \times A85$
- $Q2 = 25 \times A54 + 25 \times A63 + 25 \times A80 + 25 \times A85$
- $Q3 = 25 \times A29 + 25 \times A63 + 25 \times A80 + 25 \times A85$
- $Q4 = 25 \times A3 + 25 \times A63 + 25 \times A80 + 25 \times A85$
- $Q5 = 23 \times A3 + 33 \times A29 + 22 \times A54 + 22 \times A85$
- $Q6 = 33 \times A29 + 23 \times A63 + 22 \times A80 + 22 \times A85$

Figure S24: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from simulations of ternary mixtures of asphaltenes in toluene. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S25: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from simulations of ternary mixtures of asphaltenes in heptane. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S26: Radius of gyration of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of simulations of ternary mixtures in heptane and toluene.

Figure S27: Estimated density of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns simulations of ternary mixtures in heptane and toluene.

Figure S28: Relative shape anisotropy of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of simulations of ternary mixtures in heptane and toluene.

Figure S29: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from simulations of quaternary mixtures of asphaltenes in toluene. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S30: Aggregation number, i.e., average asphaltene cluster size from simulations of quaternary mixtures of asphaltenes in heptane. 5 ns and 20 ns moving averages are used to filter short term fluctuations of the aggregation dynamics.

Figure S31: Radius of gyration of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of simulations of quaternary mixtures in heptane and toluene.

Figure S32: Estimated density of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns simulations of quaternary mixtures in heptane and toluene.

Figure S33: Relative shape anisotropy of the asphaltene clusters over the last 40 ns of simulations of quaternary mixtures in heptane and toluene.

Figure S34: Percentage of each type of molecule involved in the formation of aggregates along the simulation of ternary mixtures. Moving averages with 10 ns windows are displayed to smoothen the short-term fluctuations of the dynamics.

Figure S35: Percentage of each type of molecule involved in the formation of aggregates along the simulation of quaternary mixtures. Moving averages with 10 ns windows are displayed to smoothen the short-term fluctuations of the dynamics.

Figure S36: For ternary mixture T1, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S37: For ternary mixture T2, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S38: For ternary mixture T3, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S39: For ternary mixture T4, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S40: For quaternary mixture M1, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S41: For quaternary mixture M2, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S42: For quaternary mixture M3, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S43: For quaternary mixture M4, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S44: For quaternary mixture M5, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

Figure S45: For quaternary mixture M6, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

5 Showcase of inhibition simulation

Figure S46: For ternary mixture T2 in presence of the nonylphenol resin inhibitor, composition of the aggregates along the simulation at 10 ns, 30 ns, 50 ns, 100 ns, 150 ns and 220 ns.

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